

PROTECTION OF THE RIGHTS OF JOINT-STOCK COMPANIES AND SHAREHOLDERS

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Annotation: This article talked about the protection of the rights of Joint-Stock Companies and shareholders in the Republic of Uzbekistan. In this case, the law “on the protection of the rights of Joint-Stock Companies and shareholders” and other legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan were established as methodological sources.

Keywords: Joint Stock Companies, personal property law, charter fund, nominal, capital.

Today, finding ways to improve the legal regulation of the organization of Joint-Stock Companies by researching the theoretical foundations of the organization of Joint-Stock Companies is one of the important issues.

For this reason, the implementation of the proposals presented below is an urgent task of the present day. They are as follows:

- 1) identification of legal signs of the organization of Joint-Stock Companies;
- 2) analysis of regulatory acts interpreting the processes of Organization of Joint-Stock Companies;
- 3) to make recommendations for further improvement of national legislation based on the data collected on the study of the processes of the organization of Joint-Stock Companies.

In addition, when talking about a joint-stock company, we also need to dwell on the issue of the legal conditions of its property.

The property that comes from the sale of shares and other securities, and which is produced and purchased by the society during its work, will be owned by it on the basis of property rights. Therefore, the law of a joint-stock company is a kind of subject of relations, that is, a legal entity, the property of which is personal property.

Y.G.Basin argues that the fundamental essence of shareholder property rights is property rights to shares that can be sold, left as heirs, pledged, and in other forms. But this means that his rights obligations are transferred to the new owner of the stock, and not to a joint-stock company, which has no obligations to buy shares in front of its employers, as well as monetary obligations. [1.19]

Based on Article 176 of the Civil Code, the property of the state as an owner under the jurisdiction of the right to conduct a deed arose, which is considered the main right of a joint-stock company that owns, uses it and gives it *tásir*, within the framework established by the Civil Code and other legal acts.

The property serves as the material basis of the independence of the activities of a Joint-Stock Company and the payment center of its debts to creditors. Under its obligations, the society responds Not only to property belonging to itself on the basis of property rights, but also to all its guarantees of obligations, such as the debts of other legal entities that it needs to pay, monetary methods. Due to this rule, legislation is established. Where the right to temporary use of property (e.g. land use) is the right to be transferred to another person, an imposition may be directed at it.

It should be noted separately that legislative acts and restrictions on the type of property paid for the share can be established in the authorized fund of the Joint-Stock Company. The shareholder can give the society property not only in the form of property rights, but also for use. In this case, the contribution of employers is determined by the amount of the fee paid for the use of this property in the entire period of its use.

With the passage of the law "on the protection of the rights of Joint-Stock Companies and shareholders", some elements of the determination of the charter fund (capital) on the list of Anglo-Saxon law entered the Legal list of the Republic of Uzbekistan. For example, in the United States and England, the following 3 types of statutory fund are distinguished: nominal capital, issued (settled) capital and paid-up capital. [2.154]

Nominal or declared capital is the total amount of capital that a society has the right to issue shares. The issued (settled) capital is a specific part of the nominal capital from which the stock is issued (settled). Paid-up capital is part of the issued (settled) Capital paid in full by shareholders. [3]

Based on Article 26 of the law "on the protection of the rights of Joint-Stock Companies and shareholders", the authorized capital consists of the ick section: declared and settled (paid) capital. The amount of the published authorized capital of the society is equal to the nominal part of all shares declared for issue. The society may issue and post part or all of the shares declared for release. Capital published in the Anglo-Saxon law register corresponds to nominal capital, covering capital issued and paid in the case of settled (paid off) capital.

The higher issued (paid) share capital determines the financial conditions of the Joint-Stock Company, and its shareholders, as well as its creditors, may

change as a result of the issuance of new shares during the activities of the Joint-Stock Company or the cancellation of issued shares.

Joint-Stock Companies can cover capital in different ways to their activities. A more common type than such coverage is the issuance of securities. Currently, the securities of the Joint-Stock Company include equity, bonds and bonds. But this list of securities of the Civil Code provides for the possibility of expansion in the interpretation established by the Securities Act and other legislative acts

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